

DCMS AI Pilot Project Report

AI-Assisted Alt-Text Creation for Heritage Collections

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1 Project

1.1 Overview

Museums house vast collections of artworks, historical specimens, and cultural artefacts. Yet, many of these objects remain digitally inaccessible to various user groups due to the lack of high-quality alternative text (alt-text). Alt-text is a brief textual description of an image that enables individuals to engage with digital content through assistive technologies such as screen readers. To enable meaningful interaction with museum collections, alt-text should convey not only essential visual information but also relevant historical and contextual significance (Chan and Hu 2023).

While alt-text is known for being essential to blind and visually impaired users, it can also benefit a broader audience, such as:

- **Neurodivergent individuals**, including those diagnosed with autism and Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), may find structured written descriptions easier to process than visual information. Clear, well-written alt-text can reduce cognitive load and support better engagement with digital content³.
- **People with learning disabilities**, such as dyslexia or language processing disorders, can benefit from simplified and accessible language in alt-text, helping to ensure equitable access to information (Linzer and Zalopany 2021).

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- **Non-native English speakers** may find descriptive alt-text easier to understand or to translate than complex visuals, especially when unfamiliar cultural references are involved.
- **Users in low-bandwidth or text-only environments** can access essential information through alt-text when images fail to load.
- **Search engines and digital assistants** also use alt-text, improving content discoverability and supporting inclusive access through voice interfaces.

This broader user base underscores the importance of high-quality, meaningful descriptions that go beyond simple visual summaries.

The most common method of alt-text creation is a manual method, where users will write a brief caption alongside every image upload. However, this individual manual approach can be time-consuming and, when it comes to museum-based objects, requires curatorial expertise to ensure accuracy and cultural sensitivity. As a result, museums often struggle to provide consistent, detailed descriptions for their collections, which limits their engagement and accessibility. This motivates the need for more automated approaches to alt-text creation.

The implementation of an AI-driven alt-text generation tool, with expert validation, can address these challenges by improving accessibility for a diverse range of users and supporting museum professionals by streamlining the creation of structured, meaningful descriptions. This reduces reliance on limited curatorial resources while maintaining quality and sensitivity. Beyond accessibility, the project offers financial and operational benefits by reducing the time and cost associated with manual alt-text generation⁴.

1.2 Aim

This project uses AI-assisted tools to develop a reliable, scalable, and human-reviewed framework for alt-text creation that combines machine-generated outputs with expert input. This best-practice model is intended to enhance digital accessibility, ensure cultural sensitivity, and provide a blueprint for wider adoption across GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) institutions.

1.3 Background

Ensuring digital accessibility has become an increasingly important priority for cultural heritage institutions, particularly in making museum collections more inclusive and engaging for a diverse range of users. The use of artificial intelligence (AI) and generative models to produce descriptive alt-text represents a promising avenue for improving accessibility while maintaining accuracy and cultural sensitivity (Feuerriegel et al. 2024).

Recent advancements in deep learning and natural language processing (NLP) have enabled AI systems to generate high-quality textual descriptions from images (Bail 2024).

⁴www.synaptiq.ai

AI tools that use advanced large language models (LLMs) have demonstrated their ability to interpret visual data and produce context-aware descriptions (Lu et al. 2024). However, despite these advances, challenges remain in ensuring that descriptions are free from bias, culturally appropriate, and contextually meaningful (Watermeyer et al. 2024).

Studies have shown that multimodal AI models, which integrate text and visual data, improve the quality and precision of automated image descriptions considerably (Prasad Agrawal 2024). A relevant study by European Parliamentary Research Service (2023) examines the role of AI in image-based museum documentation, highlighting how convolutional neural networks enhance object classification accuracy. These models rely on extensive datasets and refined training methodologies to enhance their performance, yet they still require human verification to ensure accuracy in specialized domains such as cultural heritage (Chemnad and Othman 2024).

Research from the International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (ISPRS) further explores the use of AI-driven automation in cultural heritage documentation and image annotation, highlighting the potential of machine learning in improving metadata generation for museum collections (Abate et al. 2023; Pansoni et al. 2023). Additionally, recent work by Karamolegkou et al. (2024) explores the use of vision-language models to foster cultural inclusivity in museums, emphasising the potential of alt-text to support users from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

The need for contextual richness poses a significant challenge for AI systems, which can struggle to accurately capture nuanced or culturally embedded meanings, potentially resulting in oversimplified or misleading descriptions (Karamolegkou et al. 2024). These limitations highlight the importance of involving museum professionals, accessibility advocates, and cultural experts in the creation and validation of alt-text (Foka and Griffin 2024).

Bias in AI-generated content is another major concern. Models often inherit biases from their training data, which can lead to inaccurate or insensitive representations of historical artifacts or culturally significant materials (Matthew et al. 2024). Heritage institutions adopting AI-assisted solutions must therefore implement robust bias detection and human-in-the-loop review mechanisms to ensure ethical and responsible outputs (Foka and Griffin 2024).

Building on prior research, AI-powered computer vision models have been progressively adapted to heritage contexts, incorporating museum-specific datasets to refine object recognition and improve contextual relevance (Li et al. 2023; Pansoni et al. 2023). Models such as CLIP (Radford, J. W. Kim, et al. 2021) and BLIP-2 (Li et al. 2023) offer a foundation for generating more meaningful descriptions, yet they still fall short when tasked with interpreting abstract or culturally nuanced content (Foka and Griffin 2024; Karamolegkou et al. 2024). The approach proposed in this project seeks to address these gaps through iterative model refinement, domain-specific training, and expert review (Liang et al. 2024).

The development of more advanced generative models that synthesise textual and visual information offers exciting prospects for inclusive museum experiences (Lu et al. 2024). Future systems may provide personalised alt-text based on user preferences, such as simplified explanations for children, culturally relevant descriptions, or academic insights for researchers (Prasad Agrawal 2024). Additionally, integrating AI-generated alt-text with immersive technologies such as virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) could revolutionise the way users interact with both digital and physical collections, providing richer, more accessible experiences for all (Watermeyer et al. 2024).

By leveraging AI for alt-text generation, cultural institutions have the opportunity to significantly expand digital accessibility and engagement. As museums increasingly digitise their collections, they are already taking vital steps toward greater access and inclusivity. Integrating AI-generated alt-text into this process adds meaningful descriptive context to visual records, further enhancing the accessibility and interpretability of digitised materials. However, realising this potential requires a thoughtful, inclusive approach that combines technical innovation with cultural expertise. This project aims to deliver a structured, human-centred workflow that balances automation with ethical oversight, contributing to best-practice standards for AI-assisted accessibility in the cultural sector.

2 Data

The dataset for this project consists of a selection of digitised collection items from the National Museums Liverpool, including paintings, sculptures, natural history specimens, and culturally significant artefacts. The high-resolution images are accompanied by, where available, a descriptive title, and prior textual descriptions. These human-verified descriptions serve as ground truth annotations for simple model validation and refinement.

The NML dataset is designed to capture a wide range of object types, textures, colours, and contextual significance to ensure diverse and representative data for model development. To ensure cultural sensitivity and accuracy, selected items are reviewed by museum experts and accessibility consultants. The dataset is continuously expanded and refined to improve the quality and applicability of generated descriptions across different types of museum collections, including images that need context.

To explore patterns in the visual content of the dataset, high-level image features were extracted using a pre-trained ResNet50 (He et al. 2015) model and clustered using a k-means algorithm (MacQueen 1967; Lloyd 1982) after dimensionality reduction with principal component analysis (PCA). This clustering approach enabled the identification of visually similar groups of collection items, supporting downstream analysis of descriptive patterns and accessibility needs. The test dataset was a subset of 50 objects, randomly sampled from the four clusters identified. Using the classification system described in Section 3.2.3, the dataset comprises of: *Clothing*: 11, *Statue/Bust*: 11, *Painting/Sketch*: 11, *Other*: 10, *Porcelain/Ceramic tableware*: 5, *Text based Document*: 2.

Some museum collections contain objects with potentially challenging themes, and it is essential that the generated alt-text can handle these images appropriately. To consider this, we compiled an additional expert-curated dataset consisting of 20 sensitive images from NML collections that depict themes related to slavery, colonialism, sexuality, gender, inequality, substance use, violence, and other potentially distressing historical content. This specialised dataset allows for targeted model testing and refinement to ensure descriptions remain factual, respectful, and contextually appropriate without either sanitising historical realities or using unnecessarily graphic language. The development methodology and ethical considerations for handling these sensitive materials are discussed in detail in Section 4.

3 Model development

3.1 Overview

Image-to-text models generate textual descriptions from visual content by combining computer vision with natural language processing. Unlike Optical Character Recognition (OCR), which simply extracts text from images, these models analyse the visual scene to describe objects, actions, and contextual relationships. This capability is essential for applications such as alt-text generation, accessibility tools, and content analysis.

A range of open-source vision models has been developed over the past few years, including CLIP and BLIP-2, among others. CLIP has strong vision capabilities but lacks an integrated language model for generating full descriptions, whereas BLIP-2 improves on this by stacking multiple language models on top of its vision understanding. As open-source models, they offer transparency, flexibility for customization, and cost-free access (aside from computational expenses), making them valuable for research and specialised applications.

Google Vision API⁵ represents another suite of pre-trained machine learning models with strong vision capabilities that identifies objects, faces, landmarks, and extracts text with high accuracy but lacks a large language model to generate alt-text descriptions by itself. In contrast, proprietary families of models such as GPT (Radford and Narasimhan 2018; Radford, Wu, et al. 2019; Brown et al. 2020; OpenAI et al. 2024) from OpenAI and Claude (“The Claude 3 Model Family: Opus, Sonnet, Haiku” n.d.) from Anthropic have recently integrated vision processing (“GPT-4V(ision) System Card” 2023) on top of their powerful LLMs. Unlike models explicitly designed for vision tasks, these LLM-based models with multimodal capabilities do not natively “see” images in the same way as a dedicated vision model. Instead, they rely on external vision encoders to convert images into textual or numerical representations, which the language model then interprets through transformer architectures (Vaswani et al. 2023) that excel at processing

⁵<https://cloud.google.com/vision/docs>

sequential data and capturing complex relationships between elements. These powerful multimodal systems have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in understanding complex visual scenes, reasoning visual content, and generating nuanced descriptions that incorporate both explicit visual information and implicit cultural context.

A key factor in obtaining useful outputs from these models is prompt engineering—the process of structuring input queries to guide the model’s responses. Since LLMs lack direct perceptual understanding, well-crafted prompts can help focus responses, provide necessary context, highlight key features, and reduce ambiguity in image descriptions.

Here, we develop several different pipelines (see Table 1) to generate alt-text for museum images which are based on the models mentioned above with various amounts of pre-processing and prompt development (see Figure 1 for an overview of the whole pipeline).

Table 1: Alt-text Generation Models for Museum Images

	Vision & Language Model	Prompt Selection
BLIP-2	BLIP2-flan-t5-xxl	BLIP-2-specific
GPT	GPT-4o	Base/Prompt 1 (P1)/Classification (PC)
Claude	Claude 3.7 Sonnet	Base/Prompt 1 (P1)/Classification (PC)
GPT+GV	GPT-4o + Google Vision API	Base/Prompt 1 (P1)/Classification (PC)

3.1.1 BLIP-2

BLIP-2 utilises a frozen image encoder with a querying transformer to extract visual features, which are then processed through a frozen large language model to generate textual descriptions. In particular, we select the largest available language model (11 billion parameters), FLAN-T5 XXL (Chung et al. 2022; Raffel et al. 2023), which demonstrates superior performance across vision-language benchmarks compared to other BLIP-2 configurations (Li et al. 2023).

Prompts were carefully engineered during development to optimise BLIP-2’s performance on museum image descriptions. We discovered that BLIP-2 requires substantially different prompt structures compared to LLM-based models. While LLM-based models responded well to detailed contextual instructions and specific formatting requests, BLIP-2 preferred concise, direct prompts.

3.1.2 LLMs: GPT and Claude

In this pilot project, we evaluate two prominent multimodal LLMs: GPT-4o and Claude Sonnet 3.7. These proprietary models represent the state-of-the-art in integrated vision-language capabilities. We conducted targeted prompt engineering to maximise their performance for robust alt-text generation on museum objects. The advanced reasoning capabilities of these models allow them to follow complex instructions about visual focus,

contextual elements, and stylistic requirements—enabling systematic refinement of outputs to meet specific accessibility and cultural accuracy standards. In the next section, we discuss the prompt development of these multimodal large language models.

3.2 LLM Prompt Development

Throughout this pilot project, we have evaluated several stages of prompt development. Each paragraph below provides a rough outline of the prompts that were used at each stage.

3.2.1 Base Prompt

As a control in our evaluation we include a base prompt where the model is simply asked to describe the image: “*Give a brief description of this image.*”. This was made deliberately as simple as possible in order to make comparisons with more developed prompts as part of the model evaluation.

3.2.2 Prompt 1 (P1)

Prompt engineering enables the enforcement of desired stylistic features while discouraging unwanted characteristics through the strategic inclusion of guiding information in model inputs. Alt-text has many different functions, and the exact form of the alt-text is situational - here we are aiming for general purpose alt-text that can be used across museum functions. We developed a standardised prompt through iterative testing and feedback from museum curators:

This image is {titled: {title}} and is part of a museum collection. Please give a concise description of the museum object that will be used as alt-text. Do not discuss historical context other than what is included in the image. Do not describe the background, simply focus on describing the object in the image itself and try to avoid artistic interpretations and evaluative descriptions.

This prompt is motivated by several factors:

- By incorporating the existing title through the variable title, we leverage pre-established metadata when available to anchor the description and provide immediate context for the model.
- The preference for concise descriptions ensures that the alt-text remains manageable for screen readers and aligns with user preferences for efficient information delivery (see discussion in Section 5.2).
- By explicitly limiting historical context to only what is visually evident, we prevent speculative content while maintaining factual accuracy. This approach adheres to alt-text best practices⁶ that separate visual description from interpretive context.

⁶for example: <https://design102.blog.gov.uk>

Figure 1: Project pipeline for the development of human-reviewed AI alt-text. This involves prompt development (Section 3.2), quantitative evaluation and expert feedback (Section 5) and building accessible tools (Section 6.1).

- Instructions to disregard background elements ensure descriptions centre on the museum artifact itself, not the setting of the object in the image, which in most cases here is unnecessary.
- By discouraging artistic interpretations and evaluative language, we maintain descriptive neutrality, allowing visitors to form their own impressions while receiving necessary visual information.

3.2.3 Prompt Classification (PC)

Following Prompt 1 implementation, we identified several opportunities for prompt optimization. The initial, universal prompt presented limitations when applied across our diverse dataset of museum images. For instance, directional elements such as “do not describe background” proved relevant for sculptures in museum surroundings but misleading for paintings where the “background” forms a vital part of the piece.

Our refined approach involves developing category-specific prompts tailored to different object classifications. This specialization enables more precise descriptive parameters, such as directing attention to materials and patterns when describing textiles and garments or emphasising form and dimensionality for sculptures. Category-specific prompts also allow for more accurate terminology, replacing generic terms like “object” with precise classification language (e.g., “sculpture,” “garment,” “manuscript”) that better guides the model’s descriptive focus.

To systematically categorise our diverse collection for targeted prompt application, we implemented an automated classification system using GPT-4o. This classification

method was in good agreement with human-categorised objects for a subset of 50 images. The vision-enabled model analyses each artifact image and assigns it to one of the following predefined categories: *Painting/sketch*, *Statue/Bust*, *Clothing*, *Porcelain/Ceramic tableware*, *Text-based Document*. Then, category-specific prompts are developed from the base prompt for each class. Furthermore, objects that do not fall into any of these classes are classified as *Other* and are processed using Prompt 1.

For this prompt a small additional pre-prompt (*Keep language simple, plain and informative and limit responses to a maximum of {max_characters} characters.*) was added as the start to try and make the language less verbose and technical across all outputs after feedback from the first evaluation. The *max_characters* parameter provides a straightforward and reliable method to control the length and detail of the alt-text.

3.2.4 Google Vision (GV)

To support the generation of more accurate and context-aware image descriptions, we incorporated Google Cloud Vision⁷ as an auxiliary input in the model pipeline. This service provides automated annotations, including object labelling, colour analysis, and text detection, which can be selectively integrated into prompt construction or used as post-processing checks. Rather than relying solely on raw image embeddings, this approach introduces a layer of semantic scaffolding that can highlight visually prominent features, such as artefact types, inscriptions, or textures.

In particular, the label detection proved helpful in cases where the model struggled with ambiguous forms or unusual materials. For example, Vision-derived annotations like “marble sculpture” or “ceramic vase” enabled the system to prioritise terminology more aligned with curatorial expectations. Similarly, its built-in OCR capabilities were especially useful for describing items containing visible text, such as book covers, posters, or object labels. Extracted strings were made available as metadata that could inform or constrain the output of the language model, depending on the object type.

This layered strategy allowed us to experiment with light-touch guidance mechanisms that augment, rather than replace, the model’s generative capacity. Further refinement could explore selective filtering of Vision outputs, as well as confidence-based weighting schemes, to ensure that only relevant annotations are used to inform the descriptive process.

3.3 Costs

Cost considerations for each model are detailed in Table 2. While BLIP-2 is available for download and local deployment without API fees, organizations should account for the non-negligible infrastructure expenses associated with hosting and running the model on their own hardware. Also, for the models that use the classification prompt, it is effectively

⁷<https://cloud.google.com/vision>

Table 2: Model costs per image. Assuming a 1024 x 2048 image size.

	GPT-4o	Claude Sonnet 3.7
Cost per image	0.35p	0.5p
Processed images per £1	300	200

double the cost per image as the model is called once to classify and then once to generate alt-text. We note that costs can be reduced by employing cheaper models; for example, GPT-4-mini can be used for the classification prompt, and this is roughly 10× cheaper than GPT-4o. For the addition of Google Vision, API pricing is free for the first 1000 images per month and then variable thereafter, depending on which features are being used.

4 Alt-text for Sensitive Image

When addressing sensitive historical materials, standard descriptive alt-text may not be adequate. It is critical that alt-text accurately and comprehensively conveys enough visual information for user understanding and cannot ignore historical injustices or challenging topics. Depending on context, details such as race or gender may be vitally important to our understanding, or irrelevant at other times, and therefore the models must be intelligent enough to understand these complexities⁸. A study by Kreiss et al. (2022) highlights that current reference-less evaluation metrics for image descriptions do not adequately account for context, underscoring the importance of integrating contextual information directly within alt-text to enhance accessibility for blind and low vision users.

The optimal approach to alt-text design varies according to the presentation context. When images appear alongside broader explanatory content, standard descriptive alt-text may suffice. However, this ideal scenario is not universal across digital platforms. Furthermore, screen reader navigation patterns often separate images from their contextual elements, creating potential comprehension gaps⁹. In such cases, integrating broader contextual information directly within the alt-text becomes advantageous, ensuring a cohesive understanding regardless of how the content is accessed or navigated.

Here, we therefore design and develop a new custom prompt, which extends the normal descriptive prompt to add an additional context paragraph that may be necessary to understand the image. This takes the form of additional text, developed through an iterative process, and is added to the relevant prompt to handle sensitive images:

Additionally, add a paragraph below starting with 'Additional context:' where you mention the broader context of the image. Mention additional information that will be useful

⁸www.colorado.edu/digital-accessibility

⁹webaim.org

when viewing this image considering race, sexuality, gender and class where relevant. This is a museum artifact and the description will be used for educational purposes. So it should have this format: main text

Additional context: additional text

The main text should be a maximum of 300 characters and the additional context should be a maximum of 120.

5 Evaluation

Robust evaluation of the performance of these models is necessary to build a reliable and useful product that can be used among museums and other UK public institutions. This evaluation process is non-trivial, as alt-text can be assessed not only on how accurately it extracts features from images but also on what information it contains and how effectively it communicates that information. Alt-text is subjective not just upon user priorities but also context of use - there is therefore no singular ground truth.

Assessing feature extraction is possible through methods like cross-comparison with CLIP or using metrics such as BERTScore, BLEURT or SPICE (Anderson et al. 2016; Sellam et al. 2020; T. Zhang et al. 2020) against human-written alt-text. However, these approaches rely on the accuracy of these evaluation methods themselves and neglect the fundamental question: Does the alt-text provide compelling and useful descriptions for its intended audience? Technical accuracy alone fails to capture the qualitative aspects that make alt-text effective in real-world contexts.

Additionally, it is important to get feedback when developing models from the intended user base and therefore, an external accessibility consultant was hired to conduct a small pilot study with blind and visually impaired users.

Therefore, the quality of the alt-text in this case is assessed by an expert panel of museum staff and curators at NML, as well as through feedback gathered during the pilot study.

5.1 Human Evaluation Method

To facilitate systematic human evaluation of alt-text quality, we developed an HTML-based assessment interface (Figure 2) containing our curated dataset of 50 museum objects (see Section 2). Independent evaluators were instructed to rate the alt-text accompanying each image on a (1 – 5) scale, where 1 represented a poor, uninformative, alt-text, and 5, represented a clear and informative alt-text . It is important to note that each evaluation round included multiple models being assessed concurrently, and therefore the scores for each model within a given round should be interpreted relative to one another. The order of the models below the images were randomised and the model names were made blind. The scores could then be downloaded as a CSV file from the html document. This setup

Image ID: WAG 374

Model 5

A watercolor painting depicts Inverary Castle in the distance, surrounded by trees and a grassy field. In the foreground, several deer rest and graze near a large tree. The castle features multiple turrets and is positioned amidst a serene landscape.

Rating: 1 2 3 4 5

Model 4

A detailed painting of a grand castle with multiple turrets and towers, set against a backdrop of lush green hills and a cloudy sky. The foreground features a serene body of water reflecting the castle's image. The artwork is realistic, capturing intricate architectural details and the natural landscape surrounding the castle.

Rating: 1 2 3 4 5

Model 2

The image is a watercolor landscape depicting a castle-like building in the distance, surrounded by trees and a grassy field with deer. A hill or mountain is visible in the background.

Rating: 1 2 3 4 5

Model 3

A watercolor landscape depicting a Scottish castle nestled in a valley with mountains rising behind it. In the foreground, several deer rest beneath a tall tree. The scene includes scattered trees and meadows under a soft, misty sky. The painting features delicate brushwork in muted earth tones and demonstrates the atmospheric perspective typical of Romantic-era landscape painting.

Rating: 1 2 3 4 5

Model 1

A watercolor painting depicts a scenic landscape featuring a large castle in the middle ground, framed by trees and mountains in the background. In the foreground, a few deer rest and graze on the grassy expanse. The sky is softly colored, suggesting a calm atmosphere. The style is delicate and detailed, capturing the serene essence of the scene.

Rating: 1 2 3 4 5

Figure 2: Screenshot of the evaluation html document sent to reviewers for alt-text scores. The order of both the images and the order of the models below the image are random.

Figure 3: Average and standard error from the results of the first evaluation set. 5 NML reviewers scored the 50 image test dataset for 3 different AI models (some reviewers only scored a subset of the full dataset). The dashed lines indicate the average score for each model.

allows for a streamlined setup through evaluation, which should improve the reliability and consistency of ratings across samples.

The model outputs for each model are non-deterministic, meaning each output represents a single sample drawn from the distribution of possible responses. The diversity of these outputs varies based on the temperature setting of the LLM—a parameter that controls the randomness in text generation.

We applied the same evaluation procedure to our sensitive dataset of 20 images. For this subset, reviewers were instructed to score each alt-text based on whether it provided a suitable representation of all contextual elements while maintaining cultural sensitivity—essentially evaluating if the description would stand effectively as the sole representation of the image.

5.1.1 Results

Evaluation set 1 Results from the first evaluation set, shown in Figure 3, vary depending on reviewer. Error propagation between reviewer samples is non-trivial as the results are correlated both by reviewer and by the underlying images they sample. Full error treatment is left to future work but we can still draw two main conclusion from the naive treatment considered here:

Firstly, there is a clear preference for the GPT models over BLIP-2. GPT-4o has far better vision and understanding capabilities and produces far more detailed and accurate alt-text with clarity. These results are in line with benchmarks for vision comprehension (Yue et al. 2024). Secondly, GPT-P1, which incorporates enhanced prompt development techniques, was unanimously preferred by all reviewers when compared to the GPT-Base

Figure 4: Average and standard error from the results of the second evaluation set. Four NML reviewers scored the 50 image test dataset for five different AI models (some reviewers only scored a subset of the full dataset). The dashed lines indicate the average score for each model.

model. This clear preference demonstrates that the implemented prompt development strategies significantly improved the quality of the generated alt-text.

Evaluation set 2 After evaluation set 1, the focus narrowed to the development on multimodal LLMs, which performed significantly better in the initial set compared to the open-source vision model. This evaluation set contained five different models: GPT-Base and GPT-P1 (also included in the previous evaluation set) as controls, and three additional models: (i) GPT-PC+GV - GPT-4o with Prompt classification (Section 3.2.3) and extra information added to the prompt through Google Vision outputs (Section 3.2.4), (ii) GPT-PC - GPT-4o with prompt classification and (iii) Claude-PC - Claude 3.7 Sonnet with the identical prompt classification as the GPT equivalent. The length of the alt-text outputs for these models was set, using a max character instruction in the prompt, such that all the models (excluding GPT-Base, which remained unmodified) was standardized using a maximum character instruction in the prompt, resulting in approximately 350 characters for each alt-text description.

The overall assessment was positive, with evaluators noting the difficulty in differentiating between model scores. Figure 4 shows the results of the second evaluation set. The reviewer preference for GPT-P1 over GPT-Base is again clear and, indeed, more pronounced in this evaluation set due to the lack of a lower-performing model, i.e. BLIP-2 in set 1, which meant the 1–5 scale allowed for more precise discrimination of high-performing models. In a direct comparison GPT-P1 performs better in 81% of total scores and worse in 2% of cases. Further, while the two models are identical to that used in the first round, the exact outputs are different due to the randomness in the LLMs deriving from the non-zero temperature we use.

Figure 5: Cumulative counts for each model from evaluation set 2. Lower is better; for example, a lower score at 3 means the model has a lower number 1,2 and 3 ratings and thus a higher percentage of 4’s and 5’s.

The GPT-P1+GV model outputs appeared promising, this model was not formally evaluated. The poor performance of GPT-PC+GV may be attributed to an overly convoluted prompt. With further development, the outcome could differ; however, the results indicate that large language models performed well even without the additional input from Google Vision preprocessing.

Sensitive images The dataset of 20 sensitive images was evaluated by the same expert panel of reviewers from NML and the qualitative results are shown in Figure 7. Here, GPT-Base and GPT-P1 are evaluated along with GPT-P1+Context (GPT-4o with Prompt 1 with an extension prompt for additional context) and Claude-P1+Context (identical to GPT-P1+Context but Claude Sonnet 3.7 rather than GPT-4o). There is a broader spread in scores amongst reviewers for several models; while GPT-P1+Context has a higher overall mean across the 20 scores than GPT-P1, this is not consistent on an individual reviewer level. GPT-P1+Context also demonstrated higher standard deviation in model scores for each reviewer. Notably, Claude-P1+Context emerged as the predominantly preferred model choice across all reviewers.

5.2 Accessibility Study

Participant recruitment and setup To complement the expert panel evaluations and technical benchmarks, a small-scale accessibility study was conducted to gather direct user feedback from individuals who are blind or visually impaired. This involved a series of

Figure 6: Average and standard error from the results of the sensitive image dataset. 4 NML reviewers scored the 20-image set for 4 different AI models. The dashed lines indicate the average score for each model.

moderated remote sessions with eight participants, each using their own screen reader (e.g. [JAWS](#) or [VoiceOver](#)) to interact with a set of AI-generated alt-text descriptions. Participants navigated a web-based interface that presented images alongside descriptive outputs generated by different models.

Session structure and data collection The consultancy firm *Accessible by Design* facilitated the accessibility study by conducting remote sessions with blind and visually impaired users, using our AI-generated alt-text materials to gather structured feedback and summarising user responses. The sessions followed a think-aloud protocol, allowing users to articulate their impressions in real time while engaging with the content with the assistance of a facilitator. Each session included multiple descriptions for a small set of museum images (typically three images and up to ten descriptions per session). Participants were invited to evaluate each alt-text independently and comparatively, providing both quantitative ratings (on a 1–5 scale) and qualitative feedback.

General impressions and model comparisons Quantitative feedback indicated that participants generally rated the alt-text favourably, with average scores exceeding three across all models. Claude-PC consistently received the highest ratings (with an average of 3.7), followed by GPT-PC and then GPT-P1. However, scores often shifted during the course of each session, as participants developed a more nuanced understanding of what information could—and perhaps should—be included. Early high scores were sometimes revised downward once more detailed or accurate descriptions were encountered.

Preferences for length, structure, and clarity Qualitatively, users demonstrated a preference for alt-text that is clear, concise, and front-loaded with essential details. While brevity was appreciated, users also valued contextual richness when relevant—particularly

Image 44 of 50

Image ID: 56.50.99.jpg

Model 1

A detailed depiction of an autumn scene featuring an owl perched on a tree branch adorned with red and orange leaves. Several small birds are flying and resting among the branches. The foreground shows foliage and plants, while a stream flows through rocks. The artwork uses ink and color on paper, capturing the essence of a natural autumn landscape.

Model 2

Traditional East Asian painting depicting an owl perched on a maple branch with vibrant red autumn leaves. Small birds fly nearby while a stream flows below through a rocky landscape. The scene features delicate brushwork typical of ink wash painting, with soft colors highlighting the fall foliage, water elements, and various flora in a misty mountain setting.

Model 3

A traditional painting depicting an autumn landscape featuring an owl perched on a branch amid vibrant red and orange maple leaves. Several birds are in flight and perched on branches. The scene includes a flowing stream, rocks, and foliage in the foreground, with subtle gray tones in the background. The style is delicate, with fine brushwork and a harmonious blend of colors, typical of East Asian art.

Previous

Next

Figure 7: Screenshot of the web-based interface used during the accessibility study, displaying museum images with corresponding alt-text generated by different AI models for visually impaired or blind user evaluation.

when describing historical or artistic content. Longer descriptions were sometimes perceived as tiring, especially given that many screen readers do not allow for easy rescanning of alt-text. Participants emphasised the importance of prioritising the most visually salient and informative features early in the description.

The role of lived experience in content expectations Specific content preferences varied based on users' lived experiences. For example, participants who had previously had sight or were partially sighted placed greater emphasis on detailed colour descriptions and subtle visual contrasts. There was broad agreement on the value of specifying scale and object presentation—such as whether an item was worn, placed on a pedestal, or free-standing. In contrast, overly generic or redundant language (e.g. “geometric shapes”) was discouraged. Americanised spellings and inconsistent linguistic structure were also flagged

as sources of confusion due to their impact on screen reader pronunciation and fluency.

Feedback on content focus and tone Differences emerged in how users responded to certain types of visual detail. Descriptions of background elements or staging (e.g. lighting, setting) were valued by some participants but deemed unnecessary by others. Similarly, feedback on the inclusion of mood or interpretative language (e.g. “misty atmosphere”) was mixed, although a few users explicitly welcomed emotionally resonant descriptors that conveyed the “vibe” or atmosphere of an image.

Describing sensitive or distressing content When presented with scenarios involving sensitive or historically challenging content, all participants unanimously agreed that alt-text should describe the subject matter factually and unflinchingly. Participants argued that omitting or sanitising such content would constitute a form of erasure, preventing blind users from accessing important aspects of historical knowledge. Content warnings were considered appropriate at a gallery or page level but not within the alt-text itself. Participants also expressed concern that blind audiences should not be excluded from confronting uncomfortable truths, especially within an educational or museum context.

Comparison with existing screen reader tools Feedback on screen reader support revealed varied experiences. While some users were aware of emerging AI-based image description features in tools like JAWS, these were inconsistently used or understood. One participant compared an alt-text output from JAWS with those generated by the models in the study, noting that JAWS had inferred religious context from a particular image that none of the models identified. However, this functionality was not universally available or known, reinforcing the need for museum-provided, high-quality alt-text, regardless of individual user tools.

User validation of AI-generated alt-text Participants were broadly positive about the potential of AI-generated alt-text to enhance access to museum collections. Many expressed surprise at the quality of the descriptions and enthusiasm for the technology’s role in increasing inclusion. However, the study also identified clear areas for improvement, including clarity, contextual richness, consistent spelling, and flexibility in accommodating different user needs.

Implications for design and development The study highlighted the diverse preferences and expectations of screen reader users, including the impact of prior visual experience on interpretive needs. It also underscored the ethical imperative of maintaining historical accuracy and completeness in the description of sensitive content. Several participants advocated for a more interactive model in which users could query additional details beyond the initial description.

Recommendations for future research These findings support the continued development of customisable, user-informed prompts and reinforce the importance of maintaining a human-in-the-loop process in the generation and review of alt-text. Expanding the study to include a broader participant base, including neurodivergent users or those with learning disabilities, could further enhance understanding of how alt-text supports diverse access needs. While this initial study involved a small sample size, it offered valuable insights that will inform the next stage of model refinement and prompt design.

6 Discussion

Careful prompt development with feedback from expert museum curators resulted in an improvement in model performance (here we just consider models using GPT-4o), i.e. the improvement in scores from Base to Prompt 1 across all evaluations. This prompt development resulted in more detailed descriptions while staying concise. This improvement can be explained by the reasons discussed in Section 3.2.2. Further prompt development with customisation for each object category (Prompt Classification) had no significant observable effect on model performance. Customisations for the prompt were minor for most categories, though more analysis needs to be done in this area as potential small improvements may be cancelled out by regression in other areas. Indeed, across the category *Other*, for which the Prompt Classification prompt defaulted to Prompt 1 plus the additional pre-prompt (see the end of Section 3.2.3), PC scored fractionally lower than P1 across all reviewers, though this is within 1σ error. Further prompt development is possible with useful user feedback from the accessibility study and careful iteration. However, any prompt development needs to be properly evaluated by some rigorous method to ensure the robustness of those responses.

For sensitive images, our evaluation reveals a clear preference for AI models utilising prompts that incorporate additional contextual information alongside original descriptions. The standard alt-text models (e.g. GPT-P1, GPT-PC) frequently omit crucial details from sensitive images, compromising essential context that should be accessible to visually impaired users. Claude consistently outperforms GPT in reviewer assessments, demonstrating a superior ability to identify and articulate the nuanced elements that make images culturally sensitive. In contrast, GPT-P1+Context often focuses on less relevant themes when adding additional context while missing the key reason for the object potentially requiring additional cultural context. Also in testing, GPT-4o refuses to respond in some cases when asked about challenging topics and refuses to provide detail. This was mitigated by emphasising in the prompt that this is being used for educational and accessibility purposes. However, it still affects one output in our sensitive dataset. The effective processing of sensitive images in our framework depends on accurately flagging these objects as sensitive—a classification task that our evaluation shows AI models struggle to perform reliably. Importantly, when our contextually enhanced prompts are applied

to non-sensitive images, the additional context sections become largely irrelevant, resulting in lower-quality alt-text. These findings highlight the continued necessity of human involvement in the alt-text generation pipeline, which serves not only to correctly identify sensitive content but also to safeguard the appropriateness and accuracy of model responses.

The main dataset, while comprising a diverse array of objects from NML, represents only a small subset of the museum’s extensive collection. Museums house an immense variety of artifacts, necessitating further testing to assess the robustness of alt-text models across a broader spectrum of museum objects. Particularly for the sensitive dataset, which contains a limited sample of 20 images, expanding the evaluation to include a wider range of sensitive content would provide valuable insights into model performance across more diverse and challenging scenarios.

While most of the focus was on prompt development for GPT-4o, several versions of Claude Sonnet 3.7, were evaluated alongside GPT-4o with identical prompts. Across the main evaluation, the pilot user study and particularly in the sensitive dataset the Claude Sonnet 3.7 is the preferred model by reviewers. This result correlates with visual reasoning benchmarks; on the MMMU benchmark (Yue et al. 2024), which tests comprehension across a broad spectrum of visual information, Claude 3.7 Sonnet performs slightly better (71.8%) than GPT-4o (69.1%) and significantly outperforms BLIP-2-flan-t5-xxl (35.4%), aligning with our findings. While the optimal model will depend on specific prompts, use cases, and user preferences, the ongoing rapid advancement in multimodal models suggests significant potential for improving challenging image processing and contextual understanding. The recent release of GPT-4.5¹⁰ demonstrates this trajectory, with early testing indicating a broader knowledge base and enhanced understanding of user intent, reflected in its improved MMMU benchmark performance (74.4%). Integrating such advanced models into our pipeline could yield more reliable and intelligent alt-text generation, though practical considerations remain, considering GPT-4.5’s API costs are approximately 20 times that of GPT-4o, potentially limiting its application in some contexts. As the field continues to evolve, there is exciting potential to enhance our alt-text generation pipeline by incorporating newer, more powerful multimodal LLMs as they become available.

Fine-tuning LLMs particular model on high quality existing alt-text is another possibility for model improvement, where by we can train the model on high-quality alt-text. Through our evaluation we a small sample already of excellent quality alt-text which we could use for this purpose.

6.1 User Interface

To enable easy access to the AI alt-text generation pipeline developed in this pilot project a user friendly interface was created and made available on Hugging Face. This interface

¹⁰<https://openai.com/>

Figure 8: Screenshot from the Hugging Face interface available to NML and other UK institutions. Users can upload images, customise their model and download the AI generated alt-text.

(Figure 8) allows users to upload images and select a customisable AI model, the selection tested here with options to set the length of the outputs, to generate alt-text. The generated alt-text is then available to download as a CSV file.

7 Next project phase

This project has delivered a robust pipeline that leverages state-of-the-art multimodal LLMs such as GPT and Claude, with thoughtfully crafted prompt engineering and a human-reviewed process, such that we can generate high-quality alt-text. This human-in-the-loop approach gives us confidence that the alt-text can be used in improving accessibility across a wide range of museum settings.

With input from museum staff at NML, these models have been refined to ensure cultural sensitivity and maintain contextual accuracy, and in particular, to provide suitable alt-text for images with potentially sensitive themes. Feedback from blind and visually impaired users has been generally positive, highlighting excitement about the potential of these tools to improve the accessibility landscape.

The code for this pipeline is publicly accessible [🔗](#) and we have provided an accessible user-friendly interface enabling the adoption of these models not only in NML, but also across a multitude of UK institutions where there is a great deal of interest in these kinds of tools. In particular, this interface will be integrated throughout NML as part of their daily operations for online collections, web content, internal communications, and collection databases, with funding from the pilot project covering API costs. By implementing this solution, NML will not only elevate accessibility standards across their digital presence

but also realise significant staff time savings, demonstrating how AI-assisted accessibility tools can provide both social and operational benefits for cultural institutions.

There are also many avenues to extend the impact of this work: Improving the quality and robustness of alt-text is possible through further prompt development, which can be guided by the qualitative feedback received during the pilot user study. The current implementation has demonstrated strong performance, but continuous refinement based on user experiences will ensure even greater accuracy and relevance.

Customisation represents another significant opportunity for expansion. This includes tailoring the pipeline for specific institutional needs, collection types, and individual user preferences. For museums with specialised collections—whether archaeological artifacts, natural history specimens, or contemporary art—customised prompts can better capture domain-specific nuances. Similarly, preferences for alt-text style and detail can vary among users with different visual impairments and accessibility needs. Developing flexible configuration options would allow institutions and end users to adjust these parameters according to their specific contexts.

Technology adoption must remain current and up-to-date to remain relevant. As next-generation AI models emerge, the pipeline should evolve to leverage their enhanced capabilities while preserving the human-in-the-loop validation process that ensures quality and sensitivity. Where appropriate, domain-specific fine-tuning of models could further improve performance for specialised collections or unique institutional requirements.

Furthermore, developing seamless integration solutions will be crucial for widespread adoption. Building applications and APIs that connect directly with existing museum content management systems, digital asset management platforms, and collection databases will reduce friction in implementation. This integration work should focus on minimising additional steps for staff while maximising the accessibility benefits, thereby ensuring that alt-text generation becomes an intrinsic and sustainable part of content workflows across the wider GLAM sector.

Supplementary Materials

The code for this project is available to view on [GitHub](#).

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